

Supplementary materials for

B vitamins and homocysteine levels in relation to bone mineral density: A Mendelian randomization study

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Supplementary Table 1. Descriptions of instrumental variables

SNP	Chr	Position	EA	OA	EAF	Effect	SE	P value	Mapped Gene	Exposure
rs4654748	1	21786068	T	C	0.50	1.450	0.280	8.30E-18	<i>ALPL</i>	Vitamin B6
rs2270655	4	146576418	G	C	0.94	0.066	0.018	2.20E-13	<i>MMAA</i>	Vitamin B12
rs1141321	6	49412433	C	T	0.63	0.061	0.007	3.60E-26	<i>MUT</i>	Vitamin B12
rs7788053	7	86773722	A	G	0.25	0.046	0.007	1.70E-10	<i>FUT6</i>	Vitamin B12
rs1801222	10	17156151	G	A	0.59	0.110	0.007	3.30E-75	<i>CUBN</i>	Vitamin B12
rs56077122	10	17207015	A	C	0.34	0.087	0.009	4.80E-21	<i>CUBN/T RDMT1</i>	Vitamin B12
rs12272669	11	71392610	A	G	0.01	0.510	0.007	3.00E-09	<i>MMAC HC</i>	Vitamin B12
rs34324219	11	59623378	C	A	0.88	0.210	0.007	1.10E-111	<i>TCN1</i>	Vitamin B12
rs34528912	11	59631535	T	C	0.04	0.170	0.021	2.10E-15	<i>TCN1</i>	Vitamin B12
rs117456053	11	59616831	G	A	0.98	0.160	0.026	1.90E-09	<i>TCN1</i>	Vitamin B12
rs41281112	13	100518634	C	T	0.95	0.170	0.020	8.90E-35	<i>CLYBL</i>	Vitamin B12
rs3742801	14	74759006	T	C	0.29	0.045	0.009	1.70E-13	<i>ABCD4</i>	Vitamin B12
rs2336573	19	8367709	T	C	0.03	0.320	0.007	8.40E-59	<i>CD320</i>	Vitamin B12
rs602662	19	49206985	A	G	0.60	0.160	0.007	2.40E-139	<i>FUT2</i>	Vitamin B12
rs1131603	22	31018975	C	T	0.06	0.190	0.017	4.90E-49	<i>TCN2</i>	Vitamin B12
rs1801133	1	11856378	G	A	0.67	0.096	0.008	9.50E-53	<i>MTHFR</i>	Folate
rs652197	11	71849741	C	T	0.18	0.069	0.011	1.40E-12	<i>FOLR3</i>	Folate
rs1801133	1	11856378	A	G	0.34	0.158	0.007	4.30E-104	<i>MTHFR</i>	Homocysteine
rs2275565	1	237048676	G	T	0.79	0.054	0.009	2.00E-10	<i>MTR</i>	Homocysteine
rs4660306	1	45978675	T	C	0.33	0.043	0.007	2.30E-09	<i>MMAC HC</i>	Homocysteine
rs1047891	2	211540507	A	C	0.33	0.086	0.008	4.60E-27	<i>CPS1</i>	Homocysteine
rs9369898	6	49382193	A	G	0.62	0.045	0.007	2.20E-10	<i>MUT</i>	Homocysteine
rs548987	6	25869371	C	G	0.13	0.060	0.010	1.10E-08	<i>SLC17A 3</i>	Homocysteine
rs42648	7	89977760	G	A	0.60	0.039	0.007	2.00E-08	<i>GTPB10</i>	Homocysteine
rs1801222	10	17156151	A	G	0.34	0.045	0.007	8.40E-10	<i>CUBN</i>	Homocysteine
rs12780845	10	17223244	A	G	0.65	0.053	0.009	7.80E-10	<i>CUBN</i>	Homocysteine
rs7130284	11	89148372	C	T	0.93	0.124	0.013	1.90E-20	<i>NOX4</i>	Homocysteine
rs2251468	12	121405126	C	A	0.35	0.051	0.007	1.30E-12	<i>HNF1A</i>	Homocysteine
rs154657	16	89708096	A	G	0.47	0.096	0.007	1.70E-43	<i>DPEP1</i>	Homocysteine
rs838133	19	49259529	A	G	0.45	0.042	0.007	7.50E-09	<i>FUT2</i>	Homocysteine
rs234709	21	44486964	C	T	0.55	0.072	0.007	3.90E-24	<i>CBS</i>	Homocysteine

Chr, chromosome; EA, effect allele; EAF, effect allele frequency; OA, other allele; SE, standard error; SNP, single nucleotide polymorphism.

Supplementary Table 2. Pleiotropic examinations by applying SNPs for B vitamins and homocysteine

Exposure/SNP	Mapped Gene	Effect allele	Phenotypes	Direction
Vitamin B6				
rs4654748	<i>ALPL</i>	T	Alkaline phosphatase	-
Vitamin B12				
rs2270655	<i>MMAA</i>	G	NA	
rs1141321	<i>MUT</i>	C	NA	
rs7788053	<i>FUT6</i>	A	NA	
rs1801222	<i>CUBN</i>	G	NA	
rs56077122	<i>CUBN/TRDMT1</i>	A	Platelet distribution width	+
			Female genital prolapse	+
			Mean corpuscular volume	-
			Disorders of refraction and accommodation	+
			Self-reported dupuytren's contracture	-
			Plateletcrit	-
rs12272669	<i>MMACHC</i>	A	NA	
rs34324219	<i>TCN1</i>	C	Self-reported pernicious anaemia	-
			Cause of death: hodgkins disease, unspecified	+
			ischemic stroke	+
rs34528912	<i>TCN1</i>	T	NA	
rs117456053	<i>TCN1</i>	G	NA	
rs41281112	<i>CLYBL</i>	C	NA	
rs3742801	<i>ABCD4</i>	T	NA	
rs2336573	<i>CD320</i>	T	NA	
rs602662	<i>FUT2</i>	A	Vitamin B12 female	+
			Circulating Vitamin B12 concentration in total cholesterol	+
			Folate pathway vitamin levels	+
			Vitamin B12	+
rs1131603	<i>TCN2</i>	C	NA	
Folate				
rs1801133	<i>MTHFR</i>	G	Diastolic blood pressure	-
			Mean corpuscular hemoglobin	-
rs652197	<i>FOLR3</i>	C	NA	
Homocysteine				
rs1801133	<i>MTHFR</i>	A	Diastolic blood pressure	-
			Mean corpuscular hemoglobin	-
rs2275565	<i>MTR</i>	G	NA	
rs4660306	<i>MMACHC</i>	T	NA	
rs1047891	<i>CPS1</i>	A	Homocysteine levels	+

			Homocysteine in fat mass	+
			Basal metabolic rate	+
			Platelet count	+ -
rs9369898	<i>MUT</i>	A	NA	
rs548987	<i>SLC17A3</i>	C	Mean corpuscular hemoglobin	-
			Red cell distribution width	+
			Hemoglobin concentration	-
			Primary sclerosing cholangitis	+
			Mean corpuscular volume	-
			Hematocrit	-
			Intestinal malabsorption	+
			Reticulocyte count	-
			IgA deficiency	+
			Schizophrenia	-
			Lymphocyte count	-
			Forced expiratory volume	-
			Leg fat mass	+
			Monocyte count	-
			Self-reported gout	+
			Serum urate	+
			White blood cell count	-
			Self-reported sarcoidosis	+
			Body mass index	+
			Headache	-
rs42648	<i>GTPB10</i>	G	Impedance of arm right	-
			Impedance of whole body	-
			Arm predicted mass right	+
rs1801222	<i>CUBN</i>	A	NA	
rs12780845	<i>CUBN</i>	A	NA	
rs7130284	<i>NOX4</i>	C	NA	
rs2251468	<i>HNFL1A</i>	C	Homocysteine levels	+
			Homocysteine levels in coronary artery disease	-
			Homocysteine in total cholesterol	+
			Gamma glutamyl transferase	-
			C-reactive protein	+
rs154657	<i>DPEPI</i>	A	Self-reported hypertension	-
			Mean corpuscular volume	+
			Hematocrit	+
			log eGFR creatinine in non-diabetics	-
rs838133	<i>FUT2</i>	A	Sodium in urine	-
			Mean platelet volume	-
			Hip circumference	-
			Sitting height	-

			Percentage of total caloric intake from macronutrients protein	Not reported
			Dietary macronutrient intake	-
			Total cholesterol	+
			Cholelithiasis	+
rs234709	<i>CBS</i>	C	Blood and toenail selenium levels	Not reported

SNPs in red color means pleiotropy; NA, not available; SNP, single nucleotide polymorphism. These associations were identified at the genome-wide significance level from the PhenoScanner V2, a database of human genotype-phenotype associations (<http://www.phenoscaner.medschl.cam.ac.uk/>).

Supplementary Table 3. Genetic association of B vitamins, homocysteine instruments with confounders

Exposure	Confounders	Effect	SE	<i>P</i> value
Vitamin B6	Education (SD)	-1.10E-04	2.83E-04	0.685
	Alcohol (SD of log transformed drinks per week)	-9.60E-04	1.35E-03	0.476
	Tobacco (SD of cigarettes per week)	5.82E-03	3.98E-03	0.144
Vitamin B12	Education (SD)	1.54E-03	1.69E-03	0.361
	Alcohol (SD of log transformed drinks per week)	0.013	0.012	0.254
	Tobacco (SD of cigarettes per week)	-0.022	0.014	0.121
Folate	Education (SD)	6.73E-03	0.004	0.095
	Alcohol (SD of log transformed drinks per week)	-0.025	0.019	0.196
	Tobacco (SD of cigarettes per week)	0.061	0.054	0.255
Homocysteine	Education (SD)	-2.96E-03	2.33E-03	0.204
	Alcohol (SD of log transformed drinks per week)	2.56E-03	7.97E-03	0.748
	Tobacco (SD of cigarettes per week)	0.061	0.044	0.171

Effects were obtained from the random-effects invariance weighted median model; SE, standard error.

Supplementary Table 4. Power evaluation

Outcomes	Source	Sample size	Beta _{B6}	Beta _{B12}	Beta _{folate}	Beta _{Hey}	~6% of variance		~1% of variance	
							Beta at 80% power		Beta at 80% power	
							≤ lower	≥ upper	≤ lower	≥ upper
Forearm BMD	GEFOS	8143	-0.016	-0.088	0.087	0.060	-0.13	0.13	-0.33	0.33
Femoral neck BMD	GEFOS	32,735	0.011	-0.043	0.167	-0.070	-0.063	0.063	-0.16	0.16
Lumbar spine BMD	GEFOS	28,498	7.42E-03	-0.038	-0.038	-0.071	-0.068	0.068	-0.17	0.17
Heel BMD	UKB	142,487	-4.11E-03	-0.011	-0.003	-0.046	-0.03	0.03	-0.075	0.075
Total body BMD	GEFOS	66,628	-5.52E-04	-0.083	0.069	-0.030	-0.045	0.045	-0.11	0.11
Total body BMD of age 0-15	GEFOS	11,807	-1.10E-03	-0.002	0.104	-0.015	-0.105	0.105	-0.27	0.27
Total body BMD of age 15-30	GEFOS	4180	-0.010	-0.145	0.056	-0.032	-0.18	0.18	-0.49	0.49
Total body BMD of age 30-45	GEFOS	10,062	-1.38E-04	-0.048	-0.017	-0.023	-0.116	0.116	-0.29	0.29
Total body BMD of age 45-60	GEFOS	18,805	-5.66E-03	-0.135	0.087	-0.032	-0.085	0.085	-0.21	0.21
Total body BMD of age over 60	GEFOS	22,504	6.34E-03	-0.074	0.048	-0.039	-0.077	0.077	-0.19	0.19

Betas were obtained from the random-effects inverse-variance weighted model; NA, not available.

Power was calculated using an online tool: <http://cnsgenomics.com/shiny/mRnd/>.

Supplementary Table 5. Associations of genetic prediction of circulating homocysteine with bone mineral density in different regions and age strata in sensitivity analyses.

Source	Outcome	SNPs used	Q	$P(Q)$	Weighted median			MR-Egger					
					Effect	95% CI	P	Effect	95% CI	P	$P_{intercept}$		
GEFOS	Forearm BMD	11	22.0	0.015	0.052	-0.136	0.240	0.590	0.198	-0.266	0.662	0.403	0.523
GEFOS	Femoral neck BMD	9	11.6	0.169	-0.029	-0.143	0.086	0.621	-0.148	-0.479	0.183	0.382	0.648
GEFOS	Lumbar spine BMD	9	15.7	0.047	-0.089	-0.229	0.050	0.209	0.181	-0.233	0.596	0.391	0.198
UKB	Heel BMD	11	6.2	0.801	-0.045	-0.081	-0.010	0.013	-0.035	-0.098	0.027	0.268	0.701
GEFOS	Total body BMD	11	10.1	0.432	-0.040	-0.103	0.024	0.220	-0.083	-0.193	0.026	0.137	0.285
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age 0-15	11	9.3	0.502	-0.060	-0.204	0.085	0.418	-0.183	-0.427	0.062	0.142	0.134
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age 15-30	11	10.0	0.441	-0.015	-0.260	0.230	0.905	0.003	-0.454	0.461	0.990	0.871
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age 30-45	11	6.8	0.740	0.050	-0.107	0.206	0.535	0.229	-0.050	0.508	0.108	0.047
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age 45-60	11	7.0	0.729	-0.038	-0.156	0.080	0.526	-0.067	-0.268	0.134	0.512	0.707
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age over 60	11	9.9	0.448	-0.062	-0.173	0.049	0.276	-0.085	-0.277	0.106	0.383	0.599

BMD, body mineral density; CI, confidence interval; GEFOS, GENetic Factors for OSteoporosis Consortium; The summary statistics data utilized in this study can be downloaded from the GWAS Catalog (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gwas/>) and Neale Lab (<http://www.nealelab.is/uk-biobank/>); SNP, single nucleotide polymorphism; The Q statistic was used to present the heterogeneity among estimates for each SNPs in one analysis; Effect means the value of Beta; The P value for the intercept in the MR-Egger regression was used to present the pleiotropy ($P < 0.05$).

Supplementary Table 6. Associations of genetic prediction of circulating vitamin B12 with bone mineral density in different body regions and age strata in sensitivity analyses

Source	Outcome	SNPs used	Q	$P(Q)$	Effect	Weighted median		P	Effect	MR-Egger			
						95% CI				95% CI	P	$P_{intercept}$	
GEFOS	Forearm BMD	8	6.1	0.525	-0.053	-0.216	0.111	0.528	-0.087	-0.318	0.143	0.457	0.988
GEFOS	Femoral neck BMD	7	7.7	0.260	-0.056	-0.145	0.033	0.216	0.037	-0.081	0.156	0.538	0.100
GEFOS	Lumbar spine BMD	7	11.8	0.066	-0.083	-0.207	0.042	0.194	-0.008	-0.193	0.176	0.929	0.690
UKB	Heel BMD	11	16.0	0.100	0.005	-0.018	0.029	0.659	0.009	-0.023	0.041	0.564	0.089
GEFOS	Total body BMD	11	13.2	0.212	-0.053	-0.110	0.004	0.067	-0.032	-0.099	0.035	0.345	0.056
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age 0-15	11	7.5	0.677	-0.043	-0.159	0.073	0.466	0.140	-0.013	0.293	0.073	0.025
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age 15-30	10	10.7	0.296	-0.149	-0.360	0.063	0.168	-0.054	-0.301	0.192	0.666	0.352
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age 30-45	11	9.2	0.518	-0.058	-0.176	0.060	0.333	-0.070	-0.223	0.084	0.373	0.728
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age 45-60	11	9.8	0.456	-0.115	-0.210	-0.020	0.018	-0.082	-0.192	0.028	0.142	0.222
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age over 60	11	4.4	0.928	-0.090	-0.177	-0.003	0.042	-0.025	-0.146	0.096	0.687	0.343

BMD, body mineral density; CI, confidence interval; GEFOS, GENetic Factors for OSteoporosis Consortium; The summary statistics data utilized in this study can be downloaded from the GWAS Catalog (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gwas/>) and Neale Lab (<http://www.nealelab.is/uk-biobank>); SNP, single nucleotide polymorphism; The Q statistic was used to present the heterogeneity among estimates for each SNPs in one analysis; Effect means the value of Beta; The P value for the intercept in the MR-Egger regression was used present the pleiotropy ($P < 0.05$).

Supplementary Table 7. Associations of genetic prediction of circulating homocysteine and vitamin B12 with bone mineral density in different regions and age strata in the MR-PRESSO analysis

Source	Outcome	Homocysteine							Vitamin B12						
		SNPs used	Outliers	P_Glo	P_Dis	Effect	SE	P	SNPs used	Outliers	P_Glo	P_Dis	Effect	SE	P
GEFOS	Forearm BMD	11	0	0.024	NA	0.062	0.101	0.551	8	0	0.416	NA	-0.089	0.059	0.173
GEFOS	Femoral neck BMD	9	0	0.145	NA	-0.075	0.051	0.183	7	0	0.29	NA	-0.043	0.041	0.330
GEFOS	Lumbar spine BMD	9	0	0.046	NA	-0.077	0.070	0.303	7	0	0.156	NA	-0.038	0.053	0.499
UKB	Heel BMD	11	0	0.769	NA	-0.046	0.011	1.79E-03	11	0	0.148	NA	-0.012	0.011	0.323
GEFOS	Total body BMD	11	0	0.448	NA	-0.029	0.024	0.257	11	0	0.12	NA	-0.085	0.022	3.57E-03
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age 0-15	11	0	0.469	NA	-0.014	0.053	0.793	11	0	0.594	NA	-0.004	0.040	0.921
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age 15-30	11	0	0.507	NA	-0.031	0.097	0.757	10	0	0.254	NA	-0.147	0.076	0.086
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age 30-45	11	0	0.721	NA	-0.026	0.052	0.632	11	0	0.577	NA	-0.048	0.046	0.319
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age 45-60	11	0	0.743	NA	-0.032	0.038	0.408	11	0	0.307	NA	-0.136	0.034	2.71E-03
GEFOS	Total body BMD of age over 60	11	0	0.445	NA	-0.039	0.041	0.364	11	0	0.93	NA	-0.074	0.023	8.77E-03

BMD, body mineral density; GEFOS, GEneTic Factors for OSteoporosis Consortium; The summary statistics data utilized in this study can be downloaded from the GWAS Catalog (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gwas/>) and Neale Lab (<http://www.nealelab.is/uk-biobank/>); SE, standard error; SNP, single nucleotide polymorphism; NA, not available; Effect means the value of Beta; P_Glo, p value for global test; P_Dis, p value for distortion test.

Supplementary Table 8. Associations of genetic prediction of B vitamins, homocysteine with fractures in different regions by IVW method.

Exposure	Outcome	SNPs used	Effect	IVW 95% CI		<i>P</i>
Hcy	Forearm fracture	11	6.99E-05	-1.87E-03	2.01E-03	0.944
	Femoral neck fracture	11	-8.42E-04	-2.33E-03	6.48E-04	0.268
	Lumbar spine fracture	9	1.09E-03	-3.93E-06	2.19E-03	0.051
	Heel fracture	11	4.07E-04	-7.88E-04	1.60E-03	0.505
Vitamin B12	Forearm fracture	11	5.89E-04	-6.24E-04	1.80E-03	0.341
	Femoral neck fracture	11	1.37E-04	-7.38E-04	1.01E-03	0.759
	Lumbar spine fracture	4	3.39E-04	-7.60E-04	1.44E-03	0.546
	Heel fracture	11	-2.31E-04	-9.77E-04	5.16E-04	0.545
Folate	Forearm fracture	2	2.94E-04	-4.31E-03	4.90E-03	0.900
	Femoral neck fracture	2	2.44E-03	-8.27E-04	5.71E-03	0.143
	Lumbar spine fracture	1	-1.12E-03	-3.61E-03	1.37E-03	0.378
	Heel fracture	2	-2.78E-03	-5.98E-03	4.17E-04	0.088
Vitamin B6	Forearm fracture	1	1.43E-04	-1.85E-04	4.71E-04	0.392
	Femoral neck fracture	1	-8.38E-05	-3.14E-04	1.47E-04	0.476
	Lumbar spine fracture	1	-1.19E-04	-2.81E-04	4.31E-05	0.150
	Heel fracture	1	-3.53E-05	-2.36E-04	1.65E-04	0.730

CI, confidence interval; The summary statistics data utilized for fractures can be downloaded from Neale Lab (<http://www.nealelab.is/uk-biobank>); SNP, single nucleotide polymorphism; Effect means the value of log transformed odds ratio.

Supplementary Table 9. Associations of genetic prediction of vitamin B12, homocysteine with fractures in different regions by MR-Egger and Weighted median estimate.

Exposure	Outcome	SNPs used	Effect	Weighted median			MR-Egger				
				95% CI	<i>P</i>	Effect	95% CI	<i>P</i>	<i>P_{intercept}</i>		
Hcy	Forearm fracture	11	-2.70E-04	-2.95E-03	2.41E-03	0.843	2.27E-04	-4.55E-03	5.01E-03	0.926	0.945
	Femoral neck fracture	11	-1.34E-03	-3.20E-03	5.16E-04	0.157	-1.19E-03	-4.85E-03	2.48E-03	0.525	0.835
	Lumbar spine fracture	9	9.48E-04	-4.10E-04	2.31E-03	0.171	1.67E-03	-9.86E-04	4.32E-03	0.218	0.649
	Heel fracture	11	8.91E-04	-6.46E-04	2.43E-03	0.256	1.46E-03	-1.29E-03	4.21E-03	0.297	0.405
Vitamin B12	Forearm fracture	11	1.67E-04	-1.35E-03	1.68E-03	0.829	7.23E-05	-1.80E-03	1.95E-03	0.940	0.472
	Femoral neck fracture	11	2.68E-05	-1.09E-03	1.14E-03	0.962	1.41E-04	-1.22E-03	1.50E-03	0.839	0.998
	Lumbar spine fracture	4	2.22E-04	-9.77E-04	1.42E-03	0.717	-3.47E-04	-2.90E-03	2.20E-03	0.790	0.559
	Heel fracture	11	-3.77E-04	-1.30E-03	5.43E-04	0.422	-6.79E-04	-1.83E-03	4.74E-04	0.248	0.309

CI, confidence interval; The summary statistics data utilized for fractures can be downloaded from Neale Lab (<http://www.nealelab.is/uk-biobank>); SNP, single nucleotide polymorphism; Effect means the value of log transformed odds ratio; The P value for the intercept in the MR-Egger regression was used present the pleiotropy ($P < 0.05$).

Supplementary Table 10. Associations of genetic prediction of vitamin B12, homocysteine with fractures in different regions by MR-PRESSO analysis

Exposure	Outcome	SNPs used	Outliers	P_Glo	P_Dis	Effect	SE	<i>P</i>
Hcy	Forearm fracture	11	0	0.427	NA	7.53E-05	1.00E-03	0.942
	Femoral neck fracture	11	0	0.281	NA	-8.37E-04	7.70E-04	0.303
	Lumbar spine fracture	9	0	0.254	NA	1.11E-03	5.63E-04	0.083
	Heel fracture	11	0	0.671	NA	4.10E-04	5.30E-04	0.458
Vitamin B12	Forearm fracture	11	0	0.834	NA	5.97E-04	4.68E-04	0.231
	Femoral neck fracture	11	0	0.684	NA	1.40E-04	3.89E-04	0.727
	Lumbar spine fracture	4	0	0.94	NA	3.39E-04	2.22E-04	0.224
	Heel fracture	11	0	0.642	NA	-2.23E-04	3.55E-04	0.544

The summary statistics data utilized for fractures can be downloaded from Neale Lab (<http://www.nealelab.is/uk-biobank>); SE, standard error; SNP, single nucleotide polymorphism; NA, not available; Effect means the value of log transformed odds ratio; P_Glo, p value for global test; P_Dis, p value for distortion test.

Supplementary Figure 1. Effects of genetic prediction of circulating vitamin B12 and homocysteine on BMD in different body regions and different age strata with the Multivariable Mendelian randomization adjusting education attained, smoking and alcohol usage. BMD, body mineral density; CI, confidence interval; GEFOS, Genetic Factors for Osteoporosis Consortium; The summary statistics data utilized in this study can be downloaded from the GWAS Catalog (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gwas/>) and Neale Lab (<http://www.nealelab.is/uk-biobank/>); *P value reached the significant level; SNP, single nucleotide polymorphism

Supplementary Figure 2. Forest plot for leave-one-out analysis of the significant IVW results of homocysteine with heel BMD, Vitamin B12 with total body BMD, total body BMD of age 45-60 and age over 60, with each point denoting the causal effect by IVW after removing the specific SNP on the left side. IVW, inverse variance weighted method.